

Evidence mapping of methods for incorporating economic considerations in clinical practice guideline development: a scoping review and document analysis protocol

Lungiswa Nkonki¹, Funeka Bango², Pamela Vorster³, Dachi Arikpo⁴, Gerald Manthalu⁵, Amanda Brand³, Talitha Mpando⁶, Tamara Kredo²

Correspondence to Lungiswa Nkonki; lnkonki@sun.ac.za

Abstract

Background: Incorporating economic evidence in clinical guidelines enhances efficiency in healthcare systems. Underuse of high-quality economic evidence in clinical guideline development can result in inefficiencies that undermine population health. Consequently, economic dimensions have been incorporated into guideline development in recent years. Even with these advances, the process of incorporating economic evidence into clinical guidelines is unclear. Furthermore, the selection, appraisal, and synthesis of economic evidence to be included in guideline development is often inconsistent and non-systematic. Thus, we aim to examine the literature for methods guidance on including economic evidence in developing clinical practice guidelines and summarise these methods.

Methods: We will conduct a scoping review to examine current practices in integrating economic evidence in guideline development, guided by the framework proposed by the Joanna Briggs Institute and reported according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis extension for scoping reviews. We will develop a search strategy using keywords and index terms related to economic evidence in guidelines. Two authors will search the relevant electronic databases and grey literature sources for methods manuals published within the last ten years. After screening the guideline manuals against the eligibility criteria, two authors will independently review the full texts to extract the data. We will use a narrative approach to describe the dominant methodological approaches and challenges identified in incorporating economic evidence in guideline development.

Conclusion: The results from this scoping review will provide an overview of the current methods for incorporating economic evidence in guideline development. This will provide guidance for guideline development groups in Malawi, Nigeria, and South Africa working on the Global Evidence, Local Adaptation project, but it may also be applicable to a broader global audience.

Key words – Clinical practice guidelines, Economic evaluations, Guideline development

Introduction

Clinical practice guidelines (CPGs) are fundamental tools for encouraging evidence-based and cost-effective clinical practice by informing best practices in clinical decision-making and care (Knies et al., 2019; Guerra-Farfan et al., 2022). Due to challenges affecting global health systems, including poor health systems financing and rising healthcare costs, the interest in clinical practice guidelines (hereafter referred to as guidelines) has increased. Consequently, there has been growing attention to rigorous development methodologies to produce evidence-informed recommendations (Haroon et al., 2015). In addition to clinical decision-making and improving the quality of healthcare, the benefits of guidelines include the formulation of essential medicines lists and the mapping of healthcare budgets and spending, which are all essential for reducing costs to healthcare systems (Bhaumik, 2017).

Reducing healthcare costs and providing quality healthcare are critical for achieving universal health coverage, an essential part of the Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations, 2023). However, providing quality care remains a significant challenge in many countries, resulting in avoidable mortality and consequential economic losses (World Health Organization (WHO), 2023). Worldwide, but especially in low and middle-income countries (LMICs), resource constraints in healthcare systems represent the core rate-limiting element in reducing morbidity and mortality (Manyisa & Aswegen, 2017; WHO, 2023). Consequently, one of the fundamental policy functions for guidelines is to direct investments in health (Revill et al., 2020). Economic evidence enhances the applicability of healthcare decisions (Rabarison et al., 2015). Evidence-based clinical guidelines that do not incorporate economic considerations are thus insufficient to support decision-making that promotes the best possible use of limited resources (Woolf et al., 2012). Integrating health economic evidence in guidelines can facilitate the optimisation of population health from a given budget. However, the structured use of economic evidence in guideline development could be improved (Wilkinson et al., 2021). In addition, when economic considerations are included in international public health guidelines, there need to be more recommendations on how this evidence can be translated to different contexts with varying healthcare needs and budgets. In many LMICs, the uptake of international guidance has implications for national healthcare budgets (Silverman & Lu, 2019).

Incorporating resource use considerations in guidelines is complex (Matchar & Mark, 2008). In addition to the tensions regarding the influence of economic considerations on clinical decisions for individual patients, there are challenges to incorporating economic evidence in the guideline development process. These include decisions on the choice of methods to follow, ranging from which perspective to choose for the analysis to the lack of good quality and contextually relevant health economics studies (Garrison et al., 2017; Guyatt et al., 2008).

Given these challenges, this protocol outlines the rationale, objectives, and methodology for a scoping review which seeks to examine the literature on guidance for integrating economic evidence in clinical practice guideline development and produce a summary of these methods. The scoping review will inform decision-making for the Global Evidence, Local Adaptation (GELA) project, which aims to maximise the impact of research on poverty-related diseases by enhancing the capacity of decision-makers to use global research to develop locally relevant guidelines in the field of newborn and child health in three countries, Malawi, Nigeria, and South Africa. While the core purpose of undertaking this review is to inform the use of

economic evidence in developing guidelines in the countries mentioned above, the review is anticipated to have broader applicability for guideline development groups globally.

Review aim

The review aims to identify, describe, and map approaches for incorporating economic evidence on resource use and cost-effectiveness in developing guideline recommendations.

Objectives

1. To identify publicly available guidance for methods of conducting and incorporating economic evidence into clinical practice guidelines.
2. To map and describe the recommendations to address the methodological processes, key practical steps, and lessons learnt for incorporating economic evidence in clinical practice guidelines.
3. To give an overview of the methodological challenges for incorporating economic evidence into guideline recommendations.
4. To summarise methodological challenges cited in the literature that might be relevant for applying these methods in Malawi, Nigeria, South Africa, and similar contexts.

Methods

Study design

This scoping review will be guided by the methodological framework for scoping reviews outlined in the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) Manual for Evidence Synthesis (Peters et al., 2020). Therefore, the protocol describes the planned approach to evidence searching, selection, data extraction and presentation of results. In addition, we will use the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis (PRISMA) extension for scoping reviews checklist for scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR) to guide the reporting of the findings of the scoping review (Tricco et al., 2018).

Approach to evidence searching

We will search the following databases, guideline repositories and websites of key guideline development institutions, professional societies, and Health Technology Assessment (HTA) agencies for relevant guidance documents:

- MEDLINE (PubMed)
- Guidelines International Network (GIN) database
- World Health Organization (WHO)
- National Institute for Health Care Excellence (NICE) UK
- Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network (SIGN)
- National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC)
- US Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF)
- International Society for Pharmacoeconomic and Outcomes Research (ISPOR)
- Guide to Economic Analysis and Research (GEAR)
- The Health Intervention and Technology Assessment Program (HITAP) Thailand

- The Center for Outcomes Research and Economic Evaluation for Health (CORE2-Health) Japan
- National Committee for Technology Incorporation (CONITEC) Brazil

The search strategy for electronic databases (e.g., PubMed) will include a combination of the following keywords and index terms: economic evaluation, cost-effectiveness, cost-utility, cost-consequence, cost-minimisation, health economics, health technology assessment, national healthcare economic evaluation guidelines, resource use, guidelines, clinical practice guidelines guidance, methodology, report, and manual. We will undertake a preliminary search to ensure the appropriateness of the keywords and search terms. In addition, a hand search will be conducted on the selected guideline repositories, websites of guideline development institutions, professional societies, and national HTA agencies, as listed above, to identify relevant methodology documents or manuals.

Selection of eligible documents

We will use the Endnote reference management software to manage the search output. Titles and abstracts of guidelines identified through the search will be screened against the eligibility criteria using Covidence. As we are not targeting any specific population or participant group, the screening will be guided by a modified Population, Concept, Context (PCC) framework in Table 1 (Peters et al., 2020). In addition, due to limited resources, only guidance documents published in English will be considered. We will only include guidance documents published in the last ten years, and where various versions of the same guidance exist, the most recent version will be included. Two authors will independently screen each record for inclusion. A third author will resolve conflicts about any records.

Table 1. PCC framework for eligibility of studies

Population	not limited to any specific population
Concept	Documents that provide methodological guidance on how economic evidence is incorporated into developing clinical practice guidelines.
Context	Any setting.
Types of evidence sources	We will include methodological guidelines, manuals, editorials, commentaries, or reports that provide details on the use of economic evidence, including evaluating resource use and cost-effectiveness, in developing clinical practice guidelines.

Data charting

Two reviewers will independently pilot a data extraction form (Appendix II) using two included guidance documents to further refine extraction. One reviewer will chart data from included guideline documents. Key information to be extracted consists of the following article details: Author(s), year of publication, country of origin, and methods for integrating economic evidence into guideline recommendations, including the perspective adopted, type of analysis

conducted, and the processes involved in incorporating the economic evidence. A second reviewer will review the data extraction for accuracy and quality control. Discrepancies or disagreements will be resolved by discussing or consulting a third reviewer.

Quality appraisal and presentation of results

Given the objectives of this scoping review, we will not undertake any assessment of methodological quality. Instead, a basic descriptive analysis will be performed using Microsoft Excel to summarise key characteristics of the guidance documents. We will use a narrative approach to describe the dominant methodological approaches and challenges discussed for incorporating economic evidence in developing clinical guidelines. Tables and figures, where appropriate, will be used to present a summary of data extracted related to the review question and map available guidance documents.

Discussion and dissemination

We envisage that the findings of this scoping review will provide a summary of current methods for incorporating economic evidence in clinical guideline development. This will provide guidance for guideline development groups involved with the GELA project on the methodological approaches to incorporate economic evidence into guidelines to enhance efficiency. The findings of this review will be shared with the relevant stakeholders, country partners, and funders. We will also disseminate the findings to the larger research community through publication in a peer-reviewed scientific journal and presentations at relevant conferences and events.

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Conflict of interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Authors' affiliations

¹Division of Health Systems and Public Health, Department of Global Health, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Stellenbosch University, South Africa.

²Health Systems Research Unit, South African Medical Research Council, South Africa.

³Centre for Evidence-based Health Care, Division of Epidemiology and Biostatistics, Department of Global Health, Stellenbosch University, Stellenbosch, South Africa.

⁴Cochrane Nigeria, University of Calabar, Nigeria.

⁵Department of Planning and Policy Development, Ministry of Health, Malawi.

⁶Evidence Informed Decision-making Centre, Department of Community and Environmental Health, School of Global and Public Health, Kamuzu University of Health Sciences, Blantyre, Malawi

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Appendices

Appendix I: Search strategy for PubMed

((("Costs and Cost Analysis"[Mesh] OR economic evaluation [Text Word] OR Cost-Benefit Analyses OR Cost-Utility Analysis, Cost-effectiveness Analysis OR "Technology Assessment, Biomedical"[Mesh] OR "Resource Allocation"[Mesh]) AND ("Practice Guidelines as Topic"[Mesh] OR clinical practice guidelines [Text Word])) AND ("Methods"[Mesh] OR "Health Planning Guidelines"[Mesh] OR Manual [tiab] OR Methodological Stud* [tiab]))

Appendix II: Data extraction instrument

Name of the extractor:	
Date of extraction:	
Data item	Description
Citation	
Title	
Publication year	
Country of origin	
Scope/ focus area	
Description of key proposed methods, including key steps and types of analyses conducted)	
Type of evidence recommended (resource use/cost-effectiveness)	
Type of economic evaluation (cost-benefit analysis, cost-effectiveness analysis, etc.)	
Costing method(s)	
Recommendation(s)	